

Synthesis and antimicrobial activity of some new aminobenzylated Mannich bases

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3-Bromobenzaldehyde has been condensed with piperidine, morpholine, indole, *N*-methylpiperazine to give intermediate *N*-cyclic phenylcarbinols which on condensation with acetamide, urea and thiourea, having active hydrogen functions, give the new aminobenzylated Mannich bases (1a-d, 2a-d, 3a-d). Their antimicrobial activity has been studied.

Recently, considerable research work has been carried out on the synthesis of aminobenzylated Mannich bases due to their pharmacological applications¹. In view of the importance of the biological characteristics of Mannich bases, we report here the synthesis² of aminobenzylated Mannich bases of 3-bromobenzaldehyde with suitable secondary amines and acetamide, thiourea and urea.

3-Bromobenzaldehyde reacts with cyclic secondary

amines like piperidine, morpholine, indole, *N*-methylpiperazine to form an intermediate *N*-cyclic phenylcarbinols (A), which when condensed with an amide such as acetamide, urea and thiourea, containing an active hydrogen, give aminobenzylated Mannich bases 1a-d, 2a-d, 3a-d.

Antimicrobial activity of the compounds was assayed by the cup-plate agar diffusion method³ against bacteria *Escherichia coli*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Bacillus megaterium*,

- 1, 2, 3 a Piperidine
b Morpholine
c Indole
d *N*-Methylpiperazine

Staphylococcus aureus and fungus *Aspergillus niger* at 40 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ concentration using amoxycillin (zone of inhibition 22–26 mm), ampicillin (18–24), ciprofloxacin (18–26), erythromycin (18–26) and griseofulvin (21) as standards. Compounds **1b**, **c**, **2c**, **3b**, **d** (19–21 mm) showed maximum activity against *E. coli*, **2b**, **c**, **3a**, **d** (18–20 mm) showed maximum activity against *P. vulgaris*, **1a**, **2a**, **b**, **3a**, **d** displayed maximum activity against *B. megaterium*, **1a**, **d**, **2a**, **d** (18–22 mm) exhibited highest activity against *S. aureus*. Compounds **1c**, **d**, **2b**, **d**, **3c** (19–23 mm) showed significant activity against *A. niger*. Other compounds were moderately active.

Experimental

M.ps. were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu FTIR-8400 instrument, ^1H NMR spectra on a Bruker AC-300 MHz FT NMR spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard and mass spectra on a Jeol D-300 spectrometer. All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

N-Piperidin-1-yl-3-bromophenylmethylacetamide (**1a**): Acetamide (4.40 g, 0.075 mol) was added to piperidine (4.3 ml, 0.05 mol) and stirred to get a clear solution. 3-Bromobenzaldehyde (9.2 ml, 0.05 mol) was added dropwise and the mixture was stirred for 2 h in an ice-bath at 0–5°. The resulting colloidal solution was kept at room temperature for about a week with occasional stirring. The solid separated was washed with water followed by CCl_4 and crystallized from methanol: **1a** (65 %), m.p. 146° (Found: C, 53.98; H, 6.07; N, 8.97. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_2\text{OBr}$ requires: C, 54.01; H, 6.10; N, 9.00 %); ν_{max} 3247 (NH, *sec*-amine), 1673 (C=O, amide), 569 cm^{-1} (C–Br); δ 1.45–1.57 (4H, m, piperidine, $\text{CH}_{2(\beta)}$ + $\text{CH}_{2(\beta')}$), 2.71 (3H, s, COCH_3), 2.48 (2H, m, piperidine, $\text{CH}_{2(\gamma)}$), 5.72–6.01 (4H, m, piperidine, $\text{CH}_{2(\alpha)}$ + $\text{CH}_{2(\alpha')}$), 7.17–7.41 (5H, m, ArH + C–H).

The reaction procedure leading to the **1a** was then extended to synthesize **1b–d**: **1b**, m.p. 102°, δ 1.42–1.56 (4H, s, (morpholine), $\text{CH}_{2(\beta)}$ + $\text{CH}_{2(\beta')}$), 2.68 (3H, s, COCH_3), 5.71–6.04 (4H, m, (morpholine), $\text{CH}_{2(\alpha)}$ + $\text{CH}_{2(\alpha')}$), 7.15–7.41 (5H, m, ArH + C–H), 8.04 (1H, s, NH); **1c**, 118°, δ 2.42 (3H, s, COCH_3), 7.15–7.41 (11H, m, ArH + C–H), 8.12 (1H, s, NH); **1d**, 180°, δ 1.43–1.55 (4H, m, *N*-methylpiperazine, $\text{CH}_{2(\beta)}$ + $\text{CH}_{2(\beta')}$), 2.11 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.62 (3H, s, COCH_3), 5.72–6.05 (4H, m, *N*-methylpiperazine), 7.12–7.43 (9H, m, ArH + C–H), 8.14 (1H, s, NH).

1,3-Bis-*N*-(piperidin-1-yl-3-bromophenylmethyl)urea (**2a**): To a mixture of urea (6.0 g, 0.1 mol) in water (20 ml),

ice-cold piperidine (4.3 ml, 0.05 mol) was added and stirred for 30 min. Then 3-bromobenzaldehyde (13.8 ml, 0.075 mol) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred for 2 h in an ice-bath at 0–5° and left for a day at room temperature. The resultant residue was washed with water and crystallized from methanol: **2a** (62 %), m.p. 162° (Found: C, 3.15; H, 5.65; N, 9.90. $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{32}\text{N}_4\text{OBr}_2$ requires: C, 53.19; H, 5.67; N, 9.92%); ν_{max} 3319 (N–H, *sec*-amine), 1674 (C=O, *sec*-amide), 580 cm^{-1} (C–Br); δ 1.85–2.40 (4H, m, piperidine, $\text{CH}_{2(\alpha)}$), 2.55–2.68 (4H, m, piperidine, $\text{CH}_{2(\gamma)}$), 2.71–3.03 (4H, m, piperidine, $\text{CH}_{2(\alpha')}$), 3.52–4.01 (4H, m, piperidine, $\text{CH}_{2(\beta)}$), 6.22–6.52 (4H, m, piperidine, $\text{CH}_{2(\beta')}$), 7.40–8.21 (9H, m, ArH + C–H), 8.7 (2H, s, NH).

The reaction sequence leading the **2a** was then extended to synthesize **2b–d**: **2b**, m.p. 120°, δ 1.76–2.35 (4H, m, morpholine, $\text{CH}_{2(\alpha)}$), 2.45–2.69 (4H, m, morpholine, $\text{CH}_{2(\alpha')}$), 2.72–3.08 (4H, m, morpholine, $\text{CH}_{2(\beta)}$), 6.33–6.45 (4H, m, morpholine, $\text{CH}_{2(\beta')}$), 7.46–8.25 (9H, m, ArH + C–H), 8.42 (2H, s, NH); **2c**, 105°, δ 7.05–7.65 (11H, m, ArH + C–H), 8.56 (2H, s, NH); **2d**, 132°, δ 2.2–3.1 (4H, m, *N*-methylpiperazine, $\text{CH}_{2(\alpha)}$), 2.21 (6H, s, CH_3), 3.48–3.9 (4H, m, *N*-methylpiperazine, $\text{CH}_{2(\alpha')}$), 4.32–4.94 (4H, m, *N*-methylpiperazine, $\text{CH}_{2(\beta)}$), 6.83–7.45 (4H, m, *N*-methylpiperazine, $\text{CH}_{2(\beta')}$), 7.9–8.73 (9H, m, ArH + C–H), 9.4 (2H, s, NH).

1,3-Bis-*N*-(piperidin-1-yl-3-bromophenylmethyl)-thiourea (**3a**): A mixture of thiourea (5.7 g, 0.075 mol), piperidine (4.3 ml, 0.05 mol) and water (20 ml) was stirred to get a clear solution and then treated with ice-cold 3-bromobenzaldehyde (9.2 ml, 0.05 mol). The mixture was stirred for 2 h in an ice-bath at 0–5° and left overnight at room temperature. The white residue that separated was washed with water and crystallized from methanol: **3a** (69%), m.p. 142° (Found: C, 51.69; H, 5.48; N, 9.60. $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{32}\text{N}_4\text{Br}_2\text{S}$ requires: C, 51.72; H, 5.51; N, 9.65%); ν_{max} 3168 (N–H, *sec*-amine), 1119 (C=S), 587 cm^{-1} (C–Br); δ 2.30–3.01 (4H, m, piperidine, $\text{CH}_{2(\alpha)}$), 3.12–3.28 (4H, m, piperidine, $\text{CH}_{2(\gamma)}$), 3.25–3.84 (4H, m, piperidine, $\text{CH}_{2(\alpha')}$), 4.08–4.61 (4H, m, piperidine, $\text{CH}_{2(\beta)}$), 6.52–7.02 (4H, m, piperidine, $\text{CH}_{2(\beta')}$), 7.80–8.41 (9H, m, ArH + C–H), 9.5 (2H, s, NH).

The reaction sequence leading to **3a** was then extended to synthesize **3b–d**: **3b**, m. p. 135°, δ 1.86–2.35 (4H, m, morpholine, $\text{CH}_{2(\alpha)}$), 2.43–2.65 (4H, m, morpholine, $\text{CH}_{2(\alpha')}$), 2.63–3.16 (4H, m, morpholine, $\text{CH}_{2(\beta)}$), 6.23–6.45 (4H, m, morpholine, $\text{CH}_{2(\beta')}$), 7.56–8.25 (9H, m, ArH + C–H), 8.87 (2H, s, NH); **3c**, 189°, δ 7.55–8.2 (11H, m, ArH + C–H) 8.76 (2H, s, NH); **3d**, 158°, δ 1.80–2.37 (4H, m, *N*-methylpiperazine, $\text{CH}_{2(\alpha)}$), 2.39 (6H, s, CH_3), 2.7–3.0 (4H, m, *N*-methylpiperazine, $\text{CH}_{2(\alpha')}$), 3.6–4.1 (4H, m,

N-methylpiperazine), CH₂(β), 6.1–6.5 (4H, m, *N*-methylpiperazine, CH₂(β), 7.4–8.1 (9H, m, ArH + C–H), 8.65 (2H, s, NH).

All compounds gave satisfactory nitrogen analysis.

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